

Quantum Delay Effect: Optimization & Next Steps

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Abstract. A delay line is a fundamental algorithm for building time-based effects in classical signal processing. In this work, an optimized quantum signal processing algorithm for a delay line effect is presented, derived from a preliminary version found in the literature that reproduces a classical delay line using quantum circuits. To this end, the work begins with a review of the classical concept of a delay line and the current state of the art in quantum delay line algorithms. Then, the methodology section introduces the quantum circuits used to implement both the preliminary and the optimized delay versions. The final sections present examples of the effect applied to signals and discuss how these quantum delays could be extended to encode entire audio signals, as well as their creative potential in audio and music applications.

1 Introduction

Designing signal processing effects with qubits, whether to create quantum analogues of classical effects or to explore entirely new effects with no classical counterpart, is an ongoing area of research within the field of Quantum Computer Music [1, 2]. In particular, this work presents how an optimized delay effect can be constructed using quantum circuits deriving from approaches found in existing literature.

The structure of the paper begins with this introductory section, which explains the concept of a delay line, describes the qubit encoding strategy used to implement the effect as a quantum circuit, and reviews previous work on quantum delay effects by other authors. Section 2 then introduces in detail the code used to encode the audio and how both the initial and optimized delay algorithms have been implemented. Section 3 presents the results of applying the delay circuits to signals. Finally, the results and methods are discussed in Section 4, where potential future improvements and the creative possibilities of quantum delay effects are commented.

1.1 Delay line: classical vs quantum

In classical audio signal processing—often referred to as Digital Signal Processing (DSP)—a delay line [3] is a system where an input signal is delayed in time. After this delay is introduced, the resulting signal is usually mixed back with the original, creating a subtle repetition effect

that follows the initial sound. This technique is used to enrich the audio, giving it a sense of space and reducing its dryness.

The delayed copy of the signal is usually attenuated, meaning its magnitude is lower than that of the original input. The process of delaying and adding is carried out sample by sample, as is typical in classical DSP. Thus, each sample $x(n)$ is processed according to Eq. (1):

$$y(n) = x(n) + gx(n - M), \quad (1)$$

where $x(n)$ is the original input sample, $y(n)$ is the delayed output sample, g is an amplitude attenuation factor, and M is the number of time units to be delayed [3].

This process can also be described through a diagram, such as the one in Fig. 1. This figure shows how the original signal is added to a delayed version of itself at an addition node sample by sample.

Figure 1: Classical delay line

The delay effect creates a delayed signal that is added to the original at an addition node.

In contrast, a Quantum Signal Processing (QSP) delay does not operate on a sample-by-sample basis. Instead, it performs the delay operation on all samples simultaneously. This is one of the key differences: the time evolution variable is lost, and the entire computation is done in a single step. Running the quantum circuit once is enough to apply the delay to every sample of the input sound, and the delayed signal is obtained directly upon measurement. Fig. 2 shows the diagram for this scenario.

Notice that in this figure, the system takes the entire signal X as input to showcase how the processing is carried out on all samples at once. The signal is then encoded as a quantum circuit, delayed using quantum gates, and decoded back to bits from the qubit space. Both the

delay and the addition to the original signal happen inside the quantum delay circuit module.

Figure 2: Quantum delay line

The audio signal is first encoded into a qubit-based representation. It is then delayed using quantum operations and finally decoded back into digital audio.

1.2 From analogue to quantum: the QSM audio encoding

Analog sound, encoded as a physical variable, can be translated into binary strings of ones and zeros within a computer, becoming digital sound. Unlike analog sound, digital audio is discrete, which allows for the manipulation of sound within computational systems.

To convert an analog sound signal into digital audio, the continuous waveform is discretized by sampling it at regular time intervals. This process yields a sequence of samples, each identified by a tag t_n corresponding to its position in time, and an associated amplitude value a_n representing the signal’s magnitude at that point. Together, these form tuples (a_n, t_n) . This representation preserves both the temporal structure and amplitude information of the original signal, and each tuple is subsequently encoded as a binary string of bits for digital processing and storage.

Encoding a set of samples using qubits instead of bits involves transforming digital audio into its quantum representation. The encoding used in this work is referred to as Quantum State Modulation (QSM) audio encoding [4], which maps each sample’s tuple (a_n, t_n) to a pair of qubits, as shown in Eq. (2):

$$(a_n, t_n) \longrightarrow (|a_n\rangle, |t_n\rangle). \quad (2)$$

This means that time tags and amplitude tags are each mapped to an n-qubit register. As a result, the entire audio signal can be represented as a wavefunction composed of a superposition of tensor products of each sample’s qubit pair, as expressed in Eq. (3):

$$|\psi_{QSM}\rangle = \sum_n |a_n\rangle \otimes |t_n\rangle. \quad (3)$$

Only one measurement (shot) is required to retrieve the original audio from the QSM encoding, since the information is encoded directly in the quantum states, and is not dependent on the shape of the distribution of probability amplitudes.

1.3 State of the art of quantum delay effects

Some preliminary research on QSP delay effects exists [5, 6, 7]. Paper [5] introduces a quantum computing-based model to construct a Feedback Delay Network (FDN), which is a combination of delay lines commonly used in

DSP. This work replicates a classical FDN using qubits, processing the samples one by one. It relies on quantum simulation, since some of the operations within the network violate fundamental principles of quantum mechanics. For this reason, the algorithm is considered hybrid, as it also requires classical computation. Its main strength lies in the possibility of performing large matrix–vector multiplications on quantum hardware, which could provide advantages in very large FDN scenarios, where the computational cost grows rapidly. Overall, the work is valuable in showing how quantum properties, when combined with classical computation, can open up novel computational possibilities for FDNs.

On the other hand, papers [6] and [7] propose a single quantum delay line that can be executed entirely on a quantum computer. In this case, the processing is applied to all samples simultaneously, and the circuit is run and measured only once. The present work seeks to continue this fully quantum version of the effect, building an optimized version of the delay effect introduced in these two papers and providing a corresponding code implementation.

2 Methodology

Once the concept of a delay line, the quantum audio encoding strategy, and the current state of the art in quantum signal processing delay effects have been introduced, this section presents the package used to encode audio under the QSM encoding, along with both the initial and optimized quantum delay circuits. It also compares the two circuits and explains in detail why the optimized version offers greater computational efficiency.

2.1 The Quantum Audio Package

The QSM encoding is included in the Python library called the Quantum Audio Package [8, 9], developed by the company Moth [10]. This package provides various QSP encodings and functions for quantum audio processing.

By loading an audio signal and the QSM encoding into a script, the audio can be converted into its QSM representation. Once the audio is encoded in this way, it is ready for a quantum delay effect to be applied. After the delay is implemented in the form of a quantum circuit and plugged onto the QSM representation, the audio can be retrieved by performing a single measurement. This final step (decoding) yields a delayed version of the original audio signal. See again Fig. 2 to understand this workflow.

The QAP package is based on and fully compatible with Qiskit [11], the quantum computing Python library developed by IBM. For this reason, all code developed in this work is written entirely in Python using both Qiskit and the QAP package, and can be found in *this repository* [12].

2.2 Initial QSP delay implementation

As mentioned in Section 1.3, papers [6] and [7] introduce a single delay line algorithm. The algorithm takes a sampled

signal as input and delays (shifts) it by a given number of samples towards the right, which means shifting it across the time axis.

The idea in these papers is to use a quantum adder as a quantum delay. A quantum adder [13] computes the addition of qubits, which makes it suitable for shifting the time register by a given amount. After applying the adder, the amplitudes of the initial qubits have to be set to zero to complete the operation, since the objective is to shift the signal across time—not to retain any values before the delayed start. The circuit used to perform the delay operation is therefore composed of the adder module and a zero-setting amplitude module.

The steps within the algorithm can be listed as follows:

1. Encode the signal X using the QSM encoding
2. Apply a quantum adder to delay the signal
3. Set the initial amplitudes to zero
4. Decode the signal to obtain the output Y

See Fig. 3 for a diagram of this process. Notice that the addition of the original signal to the delayed one is not accounted for in the algorithm proposed in these references. This aspect will be discussed later in Section 2.3.

Figure 3: Quantum delay line inspired by [6, 7]

In this quantum delay effect, the adder delays the signal, and the amplitude resetting gates set the initial amplitudes to zero.

Fig. 4 shows a detailed example of the quantum delay circuit for the case of 3 amplitude qubits and 3 time qubits. This implementation requires 3 ancilla qubits for the amplitude register, 1 carry qubit for the adder, 3 qubits acting as time intervals, and 3 ancilla qubits for the time register, in addition to the 6 amplitude and time qubits. The number of samples delayed by the algorithm is determined by the interval qubits, which encode the delay steps using binary notation. For example, if only the first time interval qubit is activated (set to 1), the signal is delayed by one step. If only the second is activated, the delay is two steps, and so on: $|001\rangle = 1$, $|010\rangle = 2$, $|100\rangle = 3$, etc.

While this version is functional, a more optimized implementation can significantly reduce the total qubit count. Moreover, the addition of the original signal and the delayed one is not accounted for in this delay model, despite being a fundamental step in the classical concept of a delay line, as introduced in Section 1.1. The next section explains an optimization process that leads to a more compact quantum delay algorithm, and introduces how amplitude addition can be incorporated into the quantum circuit.

Figure 4: Quantum delay circuit from [6, 7]

Both the adder and the amplitude resetting modules are composed by a set of conditional X gates. Only the amplitude and time qubits are retrieved after measurement, since they encode the signal's information.

2.3 Optimized QSP delay implementation

The delay algorithm presented in [6, 7] effectively shifts the signal in time, but the same result can be achieved using fewer qubits. This section explains how such a reduction can be achieved, and later introduces how amplitude addition can be incorporated into the circuit.

Figure 5: Optimized quantum delay circuit

Quantum delay line including the three optimizations. Only the qubits carrying information are retrieved.

The qubit count can be reduced using three methods. First, by defining a function that minimizes the number of delta time qubits required for a given sample delay M . This ensures that as the number of samples n increases, the growth in delta qubits does not scale as quickly. For this purpose, a function was implemented in the code that computed the minimum number of delta qubits. Second, a different adder can be used—one that requires fewer time ancillas. A review of different types of adder was consulted to find one that minimizes the qubit count [14]. The chosen adder can be implemented using a Qiskit function [15]. Lastly, a single qubit can be reused to reduce the number of ancilla qubits needed for the amplitude register by resetting it after each use. This reduces the ancilla qubit count from $\mathcal{O}(n)$ to $\mathcal{O}(1)$, limiting its growth regardless of the

input size. Fig. 5 shows the optimized delay circuit for a 3 time qubits by 3 time amplitudes example.

Neither the non-optimized nor the optimized delay implementations include amplitude addition. However, this operation could be introduced into the circuit by applying an additional quantum adder to the amplitude qubit register. This incorporation is left as future work, and the proposed methodology is discussed in more detail in the discussion section, Section 4.

The following section presents examples of delayed signals using both the original and the optimized circuits.

3 Results

After the implementations of the delay circuits have been described in detail, applied examples on digital signals are shown in this section to illustrate how the delays work.

3.1 Initial QSP delay results

Fig. 6 shows an 8-sample signal and its delayed version using the initial circuit from Section 2.2. The delay amount is $M = 1$, and it can be observed that it is successfully performed. The slight compression in amplitude is due to the limited number of qubits used to encode the digital amplitudes. The more qubits used, the more binary combinations are available as qubit states, and the more accurate the representation of the digital float amplitudes becomes. The amplitude qubit count is independent of the time register, so it can be increased to reduce distortion regardless of the number of time qubits. However, in this case, it has been kept to the minimum possible number for simplicity.

Figure 6: Initial delay example

Input and delayed signals using the circuit from [6, 7]. The delay length is $M = 1$.

3.2 Optimized QSP delay results

For the optimized circuit, the delay operation is also successfully performed. An example is shown in Fig. 7. A delay of $M = 1$ has been applied as well, and the distortion in amplitude is once again caused by the limited information encoding due to the number of amplitude qubits chosen.

Figure 7: Optimized delay example

Input and delayed signals using the optimized circuit. The delay length is $M = 1$.

4 Discussion & conclusion

Despite both the initial and optimized circuit implementations being fully functional, the optimized version offers a more efficient approach by significantly reducing the qubit count as the number of samples increases.

The length of the test signals has been kept at or below 2^4 . This choice is purely for development purposes, as it is easier to implement and test with simpler cases. The next step involves scaling up to the computational limits of a local machine, and subsequently using remote simulators and servers. The ultimate goal would be to encode audible audio signals, which typically have a sample rate of 44,100 samples per second. While this is currently far beyond the reach of the algorithm in its early stage, simplified signals that can be represented with fewer samples could be encoded to attempt producing preliminary audible chunks of audio in which the delay is perceptible.

Amplitude addition remains an open task. At this stage, the algorithms only compute the time shifting delay. Adding amplitudes requires encoding the original signal twice within the circuit, using extra qubits, assigning some qubits to the delay, and leaving others unchanged to be used under another quantum adder for the amplitudes later on in the same circuit. Notice that encoding twice within the same circuit does not violate the no-cloning theorem, since the encoding is simply repeated and there is no attempt of reproducing an exact state. Alternatively, multichannel strategies involving conditional operations on qubits might allow this addition without fully doubling the qubit count.

A delay line is one of the most fundamental time-based effects in classical DSP. It serves as the foundation for crafting echoes, reverbs, and a wide variety of other time-domain audio effects. As quantum hardware continues to evolve and we enter the fault-tolerant era, more sophisticated versions of these effects will become feasible on real quantum machines.

This quantum delay implementation also opens the door to exploring properties that do not need to be guided strictly by classical intuitions. This is a key aspect

of quantum signal processing: there may be entirely new ways to manipulate sound that have no classical counterpart. Classical DSP should serve as guidance and inspiration, and not as a constraint.

It is also worth noting that sound and music can embrace the noise and imperfections of today's quantum hardware. The Noise Intermediate-Scale Quantum (NISQ) era can already be creatively valuable. While we wait for more powerful computers, there is no reason not to explore the artistic potential of current quantum devices.

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